

Evangelical Church Winning All

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The Evangelical Church Winning All, was until the year 2011 known as the Evangelical Church of West Africa. It is one of the largest Christian denominations in Nigeria. Its presence is overwhelming in Northern Nigeria as it has the largest membership of indigenous groups in that region of the country. Its membership strength is in excess of six million registered followers. The Christian group that is today called ECWA was introduced to Africa by Walter Gowans, Rowland Bingham of Canada and Thomas Kent of the United States through the Sudan Interior Mission in 1893. However, when the missionaries decided to hand over the SIM related churches to indigenous leadership in 1954, ECWA became the umbrella group through which the SIM-related churches (initially in Nigeria) came together to form an indigenous body. From this time, mission stations, seminaries and bible Schools, educational institutions and hospitals and other healthcare facilities came under the control of the ECWA leadership. It is instructive to note that the vision for SIM, and by extension, ECWA was first born in the heart of a woman called Margaret (Craig) Gowans. Margaret, born in 1836 in Hamilton, Lanarkshire, Scotland was married to a brewer from Kilmarnock by the name, John Gowans (1836-1906) in 1861. She was the first individual in SIM history to conceive a vision to take the gospel to the Soudan. Her vision crystalized into the formation of ECWA and by extension the influence of the Christian group in the Muslim dominated northern Nigeria. Mr. and Mrs. John Gowan's marriage was blessed with nine children. When the family emigrated to Toronto, Canada, in 1879, Mrs. Gowans began to fervently believe that a world-wide missions was an important part of the church's work. She played a significant part in influencing two of their children to become missionaries. Annie, their oldest child travelled to China in 1892 while Walter, her fifth, went to the Sudan a year later. Bingham was reported to have recalled an important conversation he had with Mrs. Gowans when she proudly informed him that her son had been called to go to the Sudan where 60-90 million people "lived without a single Christian missionary." She was instrumental to the challenge which her son Walter, his friend Thomas Kent and later Roland Bingham took up to embrace God's heart (missions) for the people of Soudan. Their pioneering work of taking the Gospel to those of that region was one of Mrs. Gowan's idea. The acronym SIM first stood for "Soudan Interior Mission," Soudan was an older variant of the Sudan region of West Africa. After various name changes, mergers and collaborations the mission agreed to go by the name "SIM" today. In French-speaking countries it is called "Société Internationale Missionnaire." It comprises united organizations which were founded over a 100 years ago. The membership of this association includes Africa Evangelical Fellowship, Andes Evangelical Mission, International Christian Fellowship and Sudan Interior Mission. The church has grown and spread its branches across most States of northern Nigeria being about the most visible Christian denomination in most parts of the region where the influence of Islam is overwhelming. It has suffered countless violent attacks from Islamic fundamentalists but has refused to give up on its ambition of making disciples of all nations where it is found. In recent times, it also began to make vigorous attempts at launching its mission works to other parts of Nigeria, Africa and beyond. The church has a well structured administrative apparatus. Its headquarters is located in Jos, Plateau State in northcentral Nigeria and it is headed by a President. There are four other key officers of the church who administer the affairs of the ministry. They all work from the Jos headquarters of the ministry. The church has been involved in giving education to the nation's youths since its advent in the country. It started with primary and secondary education, nursing and teacher training before recently establishing two universities for training youths in various vocations of their choice. In the area of health care, the church is known to have founded and effectively managed hospitals, health centres and other health promoting facilities across the country. The church also has well funded seminaries and training colleges for training their clergy who serve as ministers, missionaries and church workers across their numerous branches.

Date Range: 1893 CE - 2024 CE

Region: Africa, Europe, North America, South America, Central America, Europe, Middle East, Asia, Australia, New Zealand

Region tags: Europe, North America, Middle East, Africa, South America, Global, South Asia, Nigeria, New Zealand, Taiwan, United Kingdom

RCCG is rapidly spreading around the world. It is represented in about 197 countries and regions worldwide.

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: The Punch Newspaper <https://punchng.com/ecwa-lost-807-members-to-banditry-conflicts-cleric/>

Notes: ECWA lost 807 members to Banditry, Conflicts - Cleric Story by Godwin Isenyo, 9th December 2022

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.arcjournals.org/pdfs/ijhsse/v9-i9/2.pdf>

– Source 1 Description: The Chronicles of SIM Missions' in Nigeria between 1893-1950

– Source 2 URL: <https://africaprimenews.com/2022/05/history-of-evangelical-church-winning-all-ecwa/>

– Source 2 Description: History of Evangelical Church Winning All (ECWA) Africa Prime News 03/05/2022

– Source 3 URL: https://www.academia.edu/98019334/Evangelical_Church_Winning_All

– Source 3 Description: Evangelical Church Winning All (ECWA) Academic Article by Rev. Prof. Stephen Oluwarotimi Baba

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.kingjamesbibleonline.org/>

– Source 1 Description: The King James Version of the Holy Bible

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Although the Evangelical Church Winning All is a Christian group well established in Nigeria, it is predominant in the northern part of the country. In northern Nigeria where it is mostly found, its existence is threatened by religious conflicts between Islamic extremists and peoples of other faiths. The violence is mostly perpetrated by the extremist groups desirous to carve out an Islamic State in Nigeria starting from the northern part of the country.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: The cultural contact between faith groups in Nigeria is competitive. This is because most of the groups seek to proselytise and win members into their fold. In most cases, the members being sought originally belong to other faiths or other groups within the same faith. This ongoing conversation between faith groups in Nigeria makes their interactions and cultural contact competitive.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: In most cases, the cultural contact between faith groups especially Christian groups is accommodating and pluralistic. Even though a number of faith groups may be focussed on the same community, region or locality to secure members into their assembly or fold, they go about it without violence or fights. However, some Islamic groups do not take kindly to groups found wooing their members as they may display violent behaviours towards the individuals attempting to convert their members. Such violence may even be visited on the convert if they decide to convert from Islam and embrace the new faith.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

Notes: It is often neutral when the conversation is between Christian or Traditional religious faith groups. However, when the cultural contact is between any of these groups and an Islamic group, the neutrality may not always be guaranteed.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: There have been several recorded violent conflicts within sample region. Churches have been burnt, property have been lost and lives have been cut short while other humans have been maimed.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Notes: The group does not involve in violent conflicts with groups outside the sample region.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Notes: Membership of the church is assigned by choice. No one is forced into the fold of the church.

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

Notes: Though children born to parents who identify as members of the church have some form of quasi-membership status accorded them, however, they get to make the decision to become full members when they become of age (become adults) to do so.

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

Notes: There are no class considerations in deciding on the membership status of people.

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

Notes: There is no specific age for assigning membership to the group. However, it is required that individuals seeking to become members must be adults

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

Notes: Membership is open to both male and female.

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– No

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: The group actively proselytises in their local environments. They also map out new areas for evangelism as they set up new branches in such places.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: Though the group does not have official political support, it has members who practice politics and have attained some form of political power in the country.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 6000000

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 2.73

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral

scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: The group believes in the authority of the Holy Bible containing 66 books; 39 Old Testament and 27 New Testament books.

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: There are a number of background events preceding the writing of some of the biblical books which have been passed on from generation to generation.

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

Notes: All scripture is inspired by God to the human beings who documented them

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

Notes: The writing of the books of the bible were inspired by God

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

Notes: The scriptures which the ECWA church holds as their authority is not alterable

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

Notes: Although the church clergy have undergone theological training to aid their proper interpretation of scriptures, other members filled with the Holy Spirit are also allowed to interpret the bible.

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: The Bible used by the group is a codified and canonised scripture

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: The church buildings are considered sacred and are used for sacred practices

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– No

Notes: The church sacred sites are not oriented to environmental features

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: The church recognises the spirit-body distinction. The group holds that although the body and spirit are two distinct components of the person, they are distinguishable. Death occurs when the spirit departs the body. While they hold that the body (flesh) cannot be part of the next phase of existence, it is the spirit that outlives the body in to the next realm of existence.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that the spirit will depart the body at the end of the bodily existence on earth and be transmuted into another realm or space where it receives its reward for the life lived here on earth. The different powers or properties the spirit has therefore is the ability to continue to exist in another realm after the earthly existence is ended. It receives due compensation for the way it conducted itself on earth and so continues to enjoy or endure the recompense or rewards as the case may be eternally.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: The spirit-mind is seen by this group as non-material and ontologically distinct from the body. It is separable from the body and also able to outlive the body.

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The church believes in the afterlife. It believes that the afterlife can be separated into two distinct locations. Some humans will inherit life abundant and bliss in the afterlife while others will have damnation, regrets and pains in the afterlife. The reward one gets is a direct consequence of the kind of life lived in this current realm of existence.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: There are two spatial locations of the afterlife. One is above while the other is either in the current location of human existence or beneath it.

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– No

Notes: The 'above' space of the afterlife is not described as vague. There is a measure of assuredness and certainty of this location. The group holds that the good afterlife location is above the skies.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– No

Notes: The group believes that though Satan will be cast into the bottomless pit, the original intention was that he and his demons (former fallen angels) would have their portion in that place eternally. Humans who allow themselves to be deceived will also have their destiny with him in hell and Hades.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: The group does not believe in reincarnation.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: Deceased members' corpses are embalmed if the burial is not planned immediately. Aside from embalming, no other treatment for members' corpses is done in the group.

↳ Cremation:

– No

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– Yes

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

Notes: The corpses of deceased members of the church are usually extended lying flat on the back in the caskets before placing them in the grave.

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– No

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: Co-sacrifices are not present in tombs during the burial of members' corpses.

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: Formal burials are present in the group. When a member dies, the family in collaboration with the church agree on a day for the burial. On the fixed date, burial programmes which have been drawn by the family and the church will be followed. Internment and entertainment of guests follows the formal burial programme and gifts are exchanged between the family of the deceased and their friends and other invited guests.

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: Cemeteries are the major places where bodies of deceased members are interred. The cemeteries are either publicly owned or church owned.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

Notes: This depends on the practice or preference of the family.

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

Notes: This depends on the practice or preference of the family.

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes in the existence of supernatural beings. They hold God (the supreme being) as the head of the supernatural beings who controls or regulates their activities.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

Notes: The group believes that the supreme being should not be represented by any molten image and that no image should be used to depict Him. However, they think of Him as having some human attributes like having big hands with which he saves those who trust in Him. They think of Him as having eyes to see, ears to hear and as one who feels our pains etc.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

Notes: Though they believe that He primarily resides above or beyond the skies, they do not equate Him with other supernatural forces that are situated in the skies as deities which operate there. In the rationalization of the group, the difference between the supreme being and other sky deities is that the former is able to operate in other realms, spheres and locations all at the same time as He is the Lord of all the earth.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: The group does not hold the supreme being as being fused with any monarch.

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Notes: The group does not hold the supreme high God as having a special connection with elites. He is rather the God of all flesh and there is no partiality with Him as He is no respecter of persons.

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that God is good and that there is no evil in Him whatsoever. He is seen as being good, perfect and loving.

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: The group holds that the supreme high God is benevolent, kind, all knowing, all powerful among others

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that all knowledge in and of the world is known to and by God. In fact they hold that He is the custodian of all knowledge.

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: The group holds that the supreme high God is all knowing

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that the supreme high God can see inside the heart/mind including the hidden motives of everyone.

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that all that one does and is capable of doing is known to the supreme high God. He is said to know the personal essence of every human.

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that God knows the end from the beginning so He knows what will happen to all individuals in the future.

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: The group holds that nothing is hidden from God. In fact they hold that there are many things in the world which are known by the supreme high God but are still being discovered by humans in a progressive manner.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that the supreme high God is the uncaused cause of all that there is in the universe. They therefore believe that He has deliberate causal efficacy in the world.

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Notes: ECWA church holds that the supreme high God can reward all actions undertaken by humans.

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Notes: ECWA church holds that the supreme high God can punish all evil actions undertaken by humans.

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that the supreme high God has direct causal efficacy in the world. However, they hold that He also uses other means to bring about actions, deeds and

events to pass through natural and unnatural means (use of other supernatural beings like angels etc)

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that the supreme is indeed good so He is expected to exhibit positive emotions.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: This only happens when it is necessary to bring balance to events on the earth. The group holds that the supreme high God could exhibit negative emotions to punish evil doing and correct bad behaviours.

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

Notes: Though God does not hunger for food, the group holds that he hungers for righteousness and for justice.

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

Notes: The ECWA church holds that God is a jealous God. He does not accept the worship of other beings apart from Himself.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: The group holds that He is the big breasted God. He is both a father to his subjects and possesses motherly instincts as well to care for and protect his followers.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

Notes: The church does not accept divination practices

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: The group beliefs that the supreme high God communicates with the living through religious specialists but He does not do so exclusively without using other means.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: The group beliefs in the existence of non-human supernatural beings. These include angels, demons, Satan etc

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

Notes: The group holds that most non-human supernatural beings cannot be seen except when there is a purpose for it.

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

Notes: Not always.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: ECWA church holds that non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world although their knowledge of the world is not unlimited unlike the supreme being.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Notes: The ECWA church believes that the non-human supernatural beings' knowledge is restricted to their areas of operation.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: The ECWA church believes that the non-human supernatural beings' knowledge is restricted to their areas of operation.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: The ECWA group believes that non-human supernatural beings have some knowledge which humans are not privy to based on their several centuries of existence and actions.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that God, the supreme being has an array of other subordinate supernatural beings. These include angels, the twenty four elders and other heavenly beings.

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

Notes: To some extent, the group believes that the supernatural beings are grouped under archangels who coordinate the activities of the angels under their band.

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Notes: Some of the principalities under the control of Satan are domain specific. Some are gods of the valley, of mountains, hills etc

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: The group beliefs that supernatural monitoring is present

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The group beliefs that there is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norms in their members and of all humans

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– No

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Notes: The church beliefs that sacred spaces like churches are meant to be hallowed and treated holy.

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Notes: The group beliefs that sacred objects like the bible are meant to be treated holy.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: The church believes that supernatural beings care about murder generally. They hold that life is sacred and should not be terminated by any other except by the State in defence of other human lives.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

↳ Incest:

– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: The church believes that bestiality, homosexuality and lesbianism are to be avoided.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

Notes: The church believes that a gossip separates friends and so discourages gossiping among members.

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Notes: The church believes in the provision of the Ten Commandments one of which states that "you shall not covet your neighbours property".

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that rituals are to be held as prescribed in order to achieve the desired result. For example, sin should not be in the lives of those approaching the altar of prayers in order to have their prayers answered.

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that performance of rituals of prayers, church attendance, etc are necessary to maintain a perfect relationship with God.

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Notes: Preaching and proselytising are major duties of the church members. Conversion of people into the fold is one of their major targets.

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Notes: The church teaches that members should not use a false scale in their business dealings with others.

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: The church believes that holiness, right living and love are pillars that hold the church together. They believe that God honours a people who are obedient to His commands and unrepentantly committed to His cause.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: The church believes that supernatural beings mete out punishments on behalf of the supreme being and as directed by him.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: It does not really matter to the group which of the supernatural beings carries out the act of supernatural punishment, what they know is that such punishments are meted out to discourage wrongdoing and to promote obedience to divine command. God is seen as the central force behind the punishment and the punishments are carried out to his pleasure.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that the supreme being also deploys impersonal cause-effect principle in meting out punishments.

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that supernatural punishments are meted out for certain purposes which may be known in many instances and unknown in others.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

Notes: The church believes that political failure in some instances are results of punishment for wrong doing.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

Notes: The church believes that defeats in battle in some instances are results of punishment for wrong doing.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

Notes: The church believes that crop failure and bad weather in some instances are results of punishment for wrong doing.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

Notes: The church believes that disaster on journeys in some instances are results of punishment for wrong doing.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Notes: The church believes that sickness or illness in some instances are results of punishment for wrong doing.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

Notes: The church believes that impaired reproduction in some instances are results of punishment for wrong doing.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

Notes: The church believes that bad luck visited on descendants in some instances are results of punishment for wrong doing.

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: The church believes that while some will be highly rewarded with crowns and made to rule over large cities in the afterlife, others will just be admitted into the afterlife through mercy as their good deeds and labours from God will be burnt in the fire but their souls saved by their profession of faith in God.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

Notes: This is an absolute teaching of the church. No pains, no crying in the afterlife as the bible says God will wipe away all tears.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– No

Notes: The church does not believe in the idea of reincarnation.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

Notes: The church believes, as the says, that children shall surround the table of those whom the Lord loves.

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Notes: Though Messianic beliefs are not present in the church, they believe that Christ is the messiah who came to the earth to restore the broken relationship between God and men. He will return to take the righteous home.

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that eschaton will hold at the end of this dispensation.

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

Notes: The date or exact time of the eschaton is unknown.

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that adherents are to keep evangelising and winning others to Christ to bring about the eschaton.

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that the divine judgement event will hold at the end of this dispensation.

↳ Restoration of the world:

– Yes

Notes: The church believes that Christ's second coming will bring a restoration of the world in such a manner that there will be order, harmony and love among all creations

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that the second coming of Christ will witness the capture of Satan and his imprisonment in the bottomless pit. However, he will be released after the millennial reign of Christ after which he will deceive humanity again and enlist their support to fight against the Christ. They will however be defeated and that dispensation will end to pave way for the final judgement.

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– Yes

Notes: After the divine judgement, a theocracy will be instituted where God will reign supreme.

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– Yes

Notes: After the divine judgement, a theocracy will be instituted where God will reign supreme.

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– No

- ↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Those who truly follow the messiah and practice the teachings of the group
- ↳ All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:
 - No
- ↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:
 - No
- ↳ Other survival condition:
 - No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The group teaches and promotes some social norms for members to follow. These norms are expected to promote togetherness and help members lead fulfilling lives of obedience to God and love for humanity.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

- Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

- Yes

↳ Courage (generic):

- Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– Yes

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– Yes

↳ Strength (physical):

– Yes

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that power, status and nobility are good. They must however be desired and pursued fairly. Power should be sought to better the lot of the majority and not to put people under bondage.

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Yes

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that beauty and attractiveness are to be desired but not exclusively as an end in themselves.

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes [specify]: The group advocates brotherly kindness, dependability and good manners among other virtues.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: The group does not promote nor teach the practice of celibacy to her members.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: The group believes sexual activities should be between married couples alone.

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

Notes: The group admonishes members (male and female) to practice monogamy and to remain faithful to their spouses.

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

Notes: The group admonishes members (male and female) to practice monogamy and to

remain faithful to their spouses.

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: The group does not encourage homosexuality, lesbianism and bestiality

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– No

Notes: The group does not encourage lesbianism queer sexual [practices and bestiality

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: Castration is never practiced in this religious group.

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: Members of the group are taught that fasting aids one's concentration during periods of praying. They also hold the view that fasting is a form of self-denial and sacrifice which moves the hands of God to answer their prayers.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Notes: The group does not place taboos on food items. They believe that all foods are clean as provided by God for human consumption. However, they teach proper hygiene and cleanness in food preparation so as not to compromise human health and wellbeing.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Notes: The group does not practice permanent body scarring or painful bodily alterations

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: Human sacrifice of any kind is not practiced in the group

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: Human sacrifice of any kind is not practiced in the group

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: Human sacrifice of any kind is not practiced in the group

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: This practice of sacrifice of property is not taught as a matter of compulsion. Members willing to support missions or other ambitious programmes of the church are welcome to give whatever comes to their minds in support of the church activities. This may be lands, buildings, vehicles or large/small sums of money as they are capable and led by the Holy Spirit.

↳ To other in-group members:

– Yes

Notes: This may happen if a member is so led to do so by the Holy Spirit.

↳ To out-groups:

– Yes

Notes: This may happen if a member is so led to do so by the Holy Spirit.

↳ Destroyed:

– No

↳ Other:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Attendance at meetings and other programmes of the church require the sacrifice of time, resources etc. Members need to move from their homes and other places of interest in order to attend

church programmes. At least, transportation and other associated costs are incurred during such movements.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: The church preaches about ethical precepts that distinguish believers from non-believers. Such sound ethical precepts include honesty, sexual chastity, respect for constituted authority etc

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Notes: Although marginalization by out-group members is not a condition for joining the group, however, it does happen. For example, when religious extremists target members of the church for attacks which sometimes result in death and fatal injuries.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: Family prayers and personal prayers are held as significant parts of a life of worship of members of this religious group

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Hours: 12

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Notes: The group holds church conventions, regular weekly programmes and other meetings which brings people together from time to time

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 100

Notes: This figure varies from region to region and could also be affected by the target group or participants for each large scale programme. For example, there are national, regional or district programmes for the entire members, children, youths, women etc. The attendance at each programme is dependent on a number of factors. A general convention will have more participants than a district youth or women meeting.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 12

Notes: This also depends on the nature of the large scale programme being held. There are annual programmes, monthly, quarterly, weekly programmes, etc

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

Notes: There are no orthodoxy checks during the church programmes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– No

Notes: There are no orthopraxy checks during meetings of the group.

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– No

Notes: Synchronic practices are not part of the group's programmes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Notes: The church does not teach the use of intoxicants in normal day life of members so they do not make intoxicants available during their meetings or programmes. This is not to say that some members do not take alcohol in their private spaces and homes in defiance to the group's position.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Notes: Extra-ritual in-group markers are not promoted nor emphasised in the group.

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Notes: Fictive kinship terminologies are used in the group although it is not widespread.

- ↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:
 - No
- ↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:
 - Yes
- ↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:
 - Yes

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

- Other [specify in comments]

Notes: The religious group has its presence in some west African countries but this entry focuses on its Nigerian assemblies.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

- No

Notes: The religious group does not provide institutional famine relief but it supports members who lack the basic necessities of life from time to time.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

- Yes

Notes: This is usually provided for the general population of the country or affected regions within the State, especially in periods of emergencies and disasters. However, distribution of these items has not always been transparent.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

- No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

- Yes

Notes: The government of Nigeria recently began formulating and implementing policies that cater for the poor. However, questions have been asked regarding the process, procedures and appropriateness

of the methods used in carrying out such exercises. The administration of poverty relief in Nigeria has been fraught with allegations of corrupt practices.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: From its early days, the group established primary and secondary schools to cater for the educational needs of her members and Nigerians in general. The group also established a school of Nursing, theological seminaries to train her clergy and recently established a university which offers quality education and moral training

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Many of the children who attend the church were trained in government schools and other private schools around them.

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: The group members interact with government officials who are in charge of government bureaucracies

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Public food storages are held by the government on behalf of all Nigerians.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: They do only when they have a major convention

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: The group encourages members to give offerings, redeem pledges and vows and to offer their tithes unto God.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The government takes taxes from all inhabitants of Nigeria

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: ECWA members interact with the Officers and men of the Nigeria Police

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group interacts with the Nigeria judicial system.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: This applies only to grievous offences against the State

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

Notes: This happens in some cases.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Notes: This may be so only by the pronouncement is made by a court of law.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group members are subject to Nigeria's legal system

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: This is acceptable in the group if their members decide to join the Nigerian army

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Members of this group speak the languages of the local communities within their environment

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They use such languages in schools, in the market and in the neighbourhood etc

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: They plan their programmes using the Gregorian calendar which is acceptable in Nigeria.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: They provide food to members whenever they are in want of food.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The government provides food in times of dire need in the country by releasing food stored away in preservation tanks and silos across the country.

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Evangelical Church Winning All, Foust, Michael. "Evangelical Belief in Reincarnation and Astrology Shockingly High, Survey Finds". Christian Headlines, October 2, 2018.

<https://www.christianheadlines.com/contributors/michael-foust/evangelical-belief-reincarnation-astrology-shockingly-high.html>.

Reference: Evangelical Church Winning All, Emmanuel O. Malomo. "PAUL'S CONCEPT OF POLITICS IN ROMANS 13:1-7 AND ITS IMPLICATIONS ON EVANGELICAL CHURCH WINNING ALL (ECWA)", September 20, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.36713/epra11243>.

Reference: Evangelical Church Winning All, Josiah, Samuel Zubairu. "RESPONSE TO EGALITARIAN VIEW ON WOMEN SUBORDINATION IN MARRIAGE: THE EVANGELICAL CHURCH WINNING ALL PERSPECTIVE", August 11, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.55559/sjahss.v1i08.42>.

Reference: Evangelical Church Winning All, "Enduring Legacy: A Trail of Doctrinal Uniqueness and Unity of the Evangelical Church Winning ALL (ECWA)." 7, no. 10 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.20431/2349-0381.0710002>.

Reference: Evangelical Church Winning All, Olajide, PhD, Grace O., and Prof. Mrs. Olatundun A. Oderinde. "An Appraisal of the Role of Women in the Birth and Growth of the Evangelical Church Winning All (ECWA), Nigeria", no. 105(2) (March 2024). <https://doi.org/10.46222/pharosjot.105.234>.

Reference: Evangelical Church Winning All, Eller, Paul H.. "A HISTORY OF THE EVANGELICAL CHURCH by R. W. Albright. Harrisburg, Pa.: The Evangelical Press, 1942. 501 Pages. \$3.50." 12, no. 1 (March 1943). <https://doi.org/10.2307/3160225>.

Reference: Evangelical Church Winning All, Bendroth, Margaret. "Evangelical from the Beginning: The Story of the Evangelical Congregational Church. Edited by Terry Heisey. Lexington, Ky.: Emeth, 2006. 381 Pp. \$24.50 Cloth; \$19.00 Paper." 77, no. 1 (March 2008). <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0009640708000371>.